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Carbon Capture, Transport and Storage (CCTS) supply chain assessment for early movers

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Abstract

The deployment of carbon dioxide capture and storage technologies requires the design of supply chains linking carbon dioxide industrial emitters with storage sites. This is illustrated here through its application to a specific case study linking a selected emitter in Switzerland to either a geological storage site in the North Sea or a domestic storage site in concrete. Based on the feasible connections for each transport mode, a network is designed for this CO₂ source. This network enables us to identify all possible combinations of transport options resulting in specific routes between the source and the chosen sink. These potential source-to-sink routes are then assessed based on their techno-economic performance. The most economical supply chains on the short- and mid-term horizons are presented in this study and allow the evaluation of the leveled costs of combined supply chains when minimizing the overall costs depending on the CO₂ uptake potential of concrete.

Keywords: Carbon capture and storage; CO₂ value chains; Waste to Energy; Networks; Optimization; Net-zero Emissions

1. Introduction

The increase in concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere due to anthropogenic emissions causes climate change [1]. Since the pre-industrial era, the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere has risen from 280 ppm to 410 ppm in 2021 [2]. In order to keep global warming below 1.5°C and limit its harmful consequences, anthropogenic emissions need to be drastically decreased [3]. Both the European Union and Switzerland aim to be climate neutral by 2050 [4, 5]. Carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies belong to the portfolio of instruments needed to achieve this climate target by decarbonizing the industry sector and by providing negative emissions. This study investigates the costs associated to the short- and mid-term implementation of carbon capture, transport, and storage (CCTS) supply chains for an early mover.

Nomenclature

CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCTS	Carbon Capture, Transport and Storage
KVA	Kehrichtsverbrennungsanlage (<i>en: waste incineration plant</i>)
WtE	Waste-to-energy

This study aims at designing CCTS supply chains to connect an industrial emitter with a storage facility. They consist of several stages, namely the capture and conditioning of carbon dioxide at a point-source emitter, the transport from the source to the sink, and the permanent storage. This study investigates the available transport modes for CO₂ deployable on the short- and mid-term time horizons (*i.e.* truck, train, barge, and ship [6, 7, 8, 9]) and the techno-economic performance of the feasible supply chains.

The industrial emitter considered in this study is the KVA Linth, which is a waste-to-energy plant located in Switzerland and emits approximately 115 ktCO₂ per year. It is considered as one of the potential pioneering chains in the project ACCSESS due to the motivation shown by the WtE sector in Switzerland to achieve climate neutrality. [10]

The CO₂ content in the flue gas of waste incinerators varies between 7 and 10%. [11] For the capture stage, we assume the use of the mature amine-scrubbing technology and a capture rate of 90%. The costs are adapted from Feron et al. [12] to the emission volume of the plant with the help of the exponent factors for cost-scale up of process equipment [13], and to the typical CO₂ concentration in the flue gas of waste incinerators.

The first considered storage technology is geological storage abroad, selected here to be the Northern Lights storage hub. The second technology is domestic storage in concrete, which can be carried out potentially at any concrete recycling plant, and selected to be the concrete recycling plant of Wollishofen in this study. [14] A concrete facility in Switzerland can mineralize on average 120 tons of recycled concrete aggregate per day. [15] Multiplied with the uptake capacity of concrete, this represents between ca. 300 and ca. 2000 t of CO₂ that can be stored in recycling concrete per year and per facility. [15, 16, 17] The possibility of storing CO₂ at several surrounding concrete recycling plants is also considered. Around the lake of Zurich, Neustark is currently collaborating with twelve concrete recycling facilities. [14] The average distance of those twelve facilities with KVA Linth is the same as the distance to the recycling plant of Wollishofen. As a first-of-a-kind, it is assumed that KVA Linth could export its captured CO₂ to all those facilities.

2. Modeling

2.1. Methodology

The data to assess the different stages of the CCTS supply chains has been gathered directly from industry, whenever possible. The specific costs for each stage are modeled accordingly. Subsequently, the levelized costs of avoided carbon are assessed by dividing the total yearly expenses of all stages of a chain by the amount of CO₂ avoided per year, thus accounting for the emissions arising from the energy and material consumption. This analysis is disregarding the biogenic share of the CO₂ emissions, in order to obtain results that could be applied to various industrial sources.

2.2. Network

The data gathered from industry enables us to identify feasible paths from a plant i to a storage site s , including transport exchange sites where transport mode changes can be effectuated. Each of these locations can be represented by a node. If there is a direct connection between two nodes, this will be represented by an edge, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Network between source node N_i that corresponds to plant i and sink node N_s that corresponds to a storage site s .

Based on graph theory, each network can be considered as a directed graph $G = (N, C)$, where N is the set of nodes and $C \subseteq \{(N_u, N_v) \mid N_u, N_v \in N \wedge N_u \neq N_v\}$ is the set of edges that connect two nodes.

The weight of each edge is characterized by a transport cost corresponding to the transport mode j available for this connection. As weights need to be unique for the analysis, parallel edges are modelled by inserting a duplicate node. Hence, one obtains a simple directed graph for each pair of source and sink nodes. The Yen's algorithm [18, 19] is applied to the corresponding graph and computes the K most economical paths from a source to a chosen sink from the perspective of transport costs.

Fig. 2. Network of feasible connections from KVA Linth to the Northern Lights storage site. The colors represent different transport modes: in orange, tank container transport by truck; in yellow, tank container transport by train; in light blue, tank container transport by barge; in dark blue, tank container transport by ship; in purple, dedicated barge transport; and in pink, dedicated ship transport.

On Fig. 2, one can observe a representative network of feasible connections on the short- and mid-term from KVA Linth to the Northern Lights storage site. The list of nodes and edges is not exhaustive but represents meaningful connections from the source node to the sink node.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Most economical supply chains

Fig. 3. Most economical supply chains (a) on the short-term and (b) on the mid-term with geological storage in Norway and (c) with domestic storage in concrete.

As displayed on Fig. 3, the most economical supply chain to achieve geological storage in Norway on the short-term is to capture and condition the CO₂ at KVA Linth, to transport it in tank containers by truck to Basel, by barge to Rotterdam, by ship to Bergen, and finally by truck to the Northern Lights storage site, with transshipments in Basel, Rotterdam, and Bergen. On the mid-term, the journey is very similar, but performed with a dedicated barge and ship on the waterways, thus directly reaching the ship terminal of the Northern Lights storage site. Potentially, there might be a need for reconditioning in Basel and Rotterdam, as the bulk transport conditions might differ from the tank container transport conditions. When realizing domestic storage in Switzerland, the carbon dioxide is transported by truck from the emitter directly to the storage site.

Fig. 4. Cost breakdown of the most economical supply chains (a) on the short-term and (b) on the mid-term with geological storage in Norway and (c) with domestic storage in concrete.

On Fig. 4, one can observe that the costs diminish by approximately 15% from the short- to the mid-term solution. As expected, the overall distance has an important impact on the costs. The journey of CO₂ to Norway covers more than 2000 km, whereas the distance between KVA Linth and the concrete recycling plant is about 50 km. Thus, performing domestic storage in Switzerland almost halves the costs of avoided carbon. This is all due to the decrease in the transport costs and of the corresponding emissions, as the remaining steps have been simulated in the same manner. For the supply chains transporting the carbon dioxide to Norway, one can observe that though the largest transport cost contributions are those from the transport on the waterways, the cost contribution from the truck transport is significant when compared to the distance covered. In the future, the costs might decrease thanks to new capture and transport technologies, the development of pipeline networks [20, 21], learning curves and economies of scale, and the deployment of closer storage sites.

The levelized costs of avoided carbon are much higher than those estimated by the Sustainability in Business Lab for the short-term solution to the Northern Lights storage site. [22] The differences lie in the assumptions about the more advanced capture technology with proprietary solvent S-26 by AKER Carbon Capture and integrated liquefaction, the retained option of building a private railway station at the capture site, the transport costs calculation, and the estimates for the storage costs on the short-term.

3.2. Levelized costs of combined supply chains

For the reason that domestic storage in concrete is more economical but the potential of storage in concrete is limited, the combination of domestic and international supply chains is evaluated to achieve the lowest levelized costs. The levelized costs of combined supply chains (i.e., those resulting by storing part of the CO₂ in a geological storage abroad and part in recycling concrete domestically) as functions of the CO₂ storage potential of concrete mineralization are displayed in Fig. 5. Considering that storage in concrete is more economical, it is assumed that this solution will always be exploited to its maximum capacity.

Fig. 5. Levelized costs of combined supply chains as a function of the CO₂ storage potential of concrete mineralization.

One can observe that if only one concrete facility is available, the variation in storage potential has a very small effect on the cost of the deployment of CCTS, as the maximal amount being storable represents only 2% of the annual emissions of KVA Linth. However, provided that it is possible to deliver and store CO₂ to all twelve concrete facilities currently involved in carbon mineralization around the lake of Zurich, the levelized costs of combined supply chains might decrease by up to 10% as shown on Fig. 5, thus having a significant impact on the carbon avoidance costs.

4. Conclusion

The cost modeling of point-to-point CCTS chains and notably of the transport stage shows a minimal cost of avoided carbon of ca. 490 EUR/tCO₂ on the short-term and ca. 420 EUR/tCO₂ on the mid-term for KVA Linth when exporting the CO₂ to the North Sea. Combined with domestic storage in concrete, the costs could decrease down to 430 EUR/tCO₂ on the short- and 380 EUR/tCO₂ on the mid-term.

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